

Evolution of Equality: The Narrative of Liberalisation

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Abstract: Narratives or myths play an important role in legitimizing knowledge and creating a sense of meaning to our lives. This article seeks to analyse the narrative of equality. I have examined the ideas of Yuval Noah Harari, the author of the book ‘21 Lessons from the 21st century’.

Firstly, the article aims to summarize Harari’s take on the narrative of equality. It traces the history of the narrative of equality and speculates how the narrative would evolve in the future. Subsequently, the author gives her own interpretation of Harari’s ideas. The article goes on to examine whether the evolution of a narrative is dependent on the rise and fall of other narratives. She seeks to analyse whether the narrative of liberalisation has had an impact on the evolution of equality as a narrative. Lastly, the article also explores equality with reference to the present-day context.

Keywords: Narrative, Equality, Liberalisation, Myth, Inequality

Introduction

Equality is defined as the “rights of different groups of people to have a similar social position or receive the same treatment.” (Cambridge English Dictionary, n.d.) Liberalisation means the deregulation of states in business. It is an economic term which advocates the existence of both public and private sectors. After the world saw the failure of the systems of capitalism and

communism, the revolution of liberalisation came up. Liberalisation was founded on the principles of both capitalism and communism; where free markets and the private sector would exist simultaneously with the public sector. Thus, it was founded on the ideals of both freedom and equality.

In the present-day society, we are losing faith in the narrative of liberalisation. This article attempts to examine how we understand equality in the present-day society as we are viewing liberalisation with a sceptical lens.

Harari's Insights on Equality

The chapter on Equality opens with Harari's blunt claim that the 21st century may create the most unequal societies in history. As we are progressing, the Internet and globalization may widen the rift between classes let alone lead to equality. The gap between the classes may heighten extensively and it will lead to speciation where the species will divide into separate biological castes.

Harari goes on to trace the history of equality. He claims that although inequality prevailed in the Stone Age, the hunter-gatherers had a far more egalitarian society. This is because the *Homo sapiens* of the stone age owned very little property. Harari believes that property is a precondition for long term inequality. During the agricultural revolution the *Homo sapiens* started owning more property leading to increase in inequality. The human beings of that time accepted this inequality not as natural but divinely ordained. In these societies "hierarchy was not just the norm but also the ideal" (Harari, 2018). Priests and philosophers at that time described how it was important to have hierarchies in the societies and that equality would bring chaos.

In the modern era, equality became a way of life. This was because of the influence of communism and liberalism. Moreover, the

industrial revolution gave importance to the masses. The state began to invest in healthcare and education for the masses. Hence the twentieth century saw a reduction in inequality and it was a far more equal society as compared to the pre-modern times.

People expected that the spirit of equality would rise in the 21st century with globalization and liberalisation. However, this has not been the case. There are some groups and communities that monopolise the fruits of globalisation in the present times. Harari claims that this could get worse in the future. “The rise of AI might eliminate the economic and political power of most humans. At the same time improvements in biotechnology might make it possible to translate economic inequality into biological inequality” (Harari, 2018).

Harari gives the following example: if there are new expensive treatments for extending life or boosting one’s cognitive skills then the gap between rich and poor would further increase. Biotechnology and AI together may divide the *Homo sapiens* into a small class of superhumans and a large class of incompetent human beings.

Harari subsequently attempts to give a solution to this problem and claims that if human beings want to prevent this from happening, they must regulate the ownership of data. Data is the most important asset of future generations. Giving us insights from history, Harari claims that in the pre-modern times the most important asset was land. Unequal distribution of land among the people caused inequality and divided the society into aristocrats and commoners.

In the modern era the most important assets were the machines and factories. Unequal distribution of these important assets

divided the society into the rich capitalists (haves) and the proletarians (have-nots).

However, in the present day, the most important asset is data. The race to obtain more data has already been started by the big data giants like Google and Facebook. These data giants capture our attention in exchange for information, services and entertainment. They then sell our attention to advertisers. The true business of these data giants is not to sell us advertisements but to capture our attention and accumulate information about us. This data is far more worth than any advertising revenue. Hence, we are not their customers but their products.

This hoarding of data opens radical business avenues and models. These business models transfer the power of choosing and buying from humans to algorithms. Harari believes that the first victim of such a business model would be the advertising industry itself. If algorithms have the power to choose and buy things for human beings, then the traditional advertising industry would cease to exist.

“By bringing together enough data and enough computing power; the data giants could hack the deepest secrets of our life, and then use this knowledge not just to make choices for us or manipulate us, but also re-engineer organic life and to create inorganic life forms” (Harari, 2018).

Thus, ownership of data is the most important question that needs to be answered if we do not want our socio-political system to collapse. Harari believes that if governments are given the power to nationalize the data it would give rise to dictatorships. Private ownership of data is an ambiguous option because it is difficult to regulate data since it is everywhere and nowhere at the same time. Moreover, several copies of the same data can be created. Harari closes the chapter by suggesting that perhaps networked algorithms could form a foundation for a global human community that could

collectively own all the data. Thus, preventing misuse of data or concentration of data into the hands of a few.(Harari, 2018).

Our Interpretation

In the book *Sapiens*, Yuval Noah Harari (2014) introduces the term myth. Harari reflects upon the ‘cognitive revolution’ of human beings. The cognitive revolution gave birth to the formation of legends, myths, and imagined realities. He defines imagined reality or myth as something that exists because people believe in its existence. For instance, two Catholics would believe in the myth of a church. States believe in the existence of ‘nations’ which Anderson calls imagined communities (Anderson, 2006). This constitutes national myths. Lawyers believe in the same code of law which constitutes a legal myth. Thus, we are surrounded by common myths that exist because *Homo sapiens* choose to believe in their existence. They could be ranging from Democracy, law, and nation-states to the biggest myth of humankind: Human Rights. The institution of Human Rights which was adopted by the United Nations is the greatest myth that humankind believes.

Harari claims that these ‘myths’ first originated in the human imagination. Since all human beings believe in these myths, human beings can co-ordinate and co-exist. Human beings dominate all the other species on Earth because of common ‘myths’ that they believe in.

“Yet none of these things exists outside the stories that people invent and tell one another. There are no gods in the universe, no nations, no money, no human rights, no laws and no justice outside the common imagination of human beings” (Harari, 2014).

In the book *The Postmodern Condition*, Lyotard introduces the concept of a narrative. He defines narrative as “stories about history and goals of the human race that legitimize and ground knowledge and cultural practices” (Lyotard, 1984).

The concept of a Myth is similar to Narratives in many ways. Firstly, both of them are stories that exist in people’s collective imagination. They are created by humans and exist because the human race chooses to believe in it. Secondly, both of them help to create meaning in life. Finally, these “stories” according to Harari help *Homo sapiens* to coordinate their activities in large numbers which ensures the functioning of states and societies. For Lyotard, narratives enable legitimization of knowledge and other cultural practices. From this research, we are only looking at how Harari’s idea of myth is similar to Lyotard’s idea of a narrative.

I explained this relation in order to conclude that equality is also a narrative or a myth. In my opinion, narratives change or evolve with time. Moreover, how one narrative creates meaning is often dependent on the rise and fall of other narratives.

Let us analyse how other narratives have shaped the narrative of equality. For instance, ideas of religion and divinity dominated the pre-modern period. This had a significant impact on the way the narrative of inequality was legitimized in the society. For instance, people believed that hierarchy was divine, it was the way of life and that equality would lead to chaos. In fact, the Caste System in India was based on this foundation. It was believed that the four *varnas* came about from the different organs of Lord Brahma. Thus, division and inequality were associated with divinity.¹

¹ *The caste system* [ushistory.org]. (n.d.). US History. <https://www.ushistory.org/civ/8b.asp>

In the modern era, the narratives of communism influenced the way in which we looked at equality. Equality then became a way of life. In the postmodern era the narrative of liberalisation became the dominant narrative. Liberalisation is founded on the narratives of both freedom and equality. A paper in the American Political Science Review claims that “The doctrine that is needed to explain and to guide the international relations of the twentieth, or for that matter any other, century must rest on these dogmas: Peoples, like individuals, are not by nature free; peoples, like individuals, are not by nature equal. Authority is prior to liberty and makes liberty possible” (Dunning, 1923). Thus, with the advent of ideas of liberalisation it was believed that freedom makes equality plausible. Moreover, it was believed that a society is incompatible with absolute equality or absolute liberty. However, it is “an indispensable guarantee of proportional equality and of qualified and practicable liberty” (Dunning, 1923).

Thus, our ideas about the narrative of equality changed from the modern times after the advent of liberalisation. There was emphasis on the freedom of the individual; it was believed that individuals could take rational decisions and ensure equality at the same time. Thus, liberty was believed as something that made equality possible.

However, some political philosophers and thinkers like Lord Acton believed that liberty and equality are antithetical in nature. Nevertheless, the narrative of liberalisation was irresistible and influenced the way in which we looked at the narrative of equality. We will talk about equality in the present day and the influence of liberalisation on equality a little later in the article.

I agree with Harari to some extent that the 21st century may create the most unequal societies as there would be speciation.

However, how we would view the narrative of equality in the future would significantly depend on the rise and fall of other narratives in future. History attests that other narratives have shaped the way in which we understand the narrative of equality. Thus, in the future, the narratives that dominate would also have an influence on how we comprehend equality.

Harari gives an example in his book where he suggests that when speciation occurs, humans would be divided into superhumans and a class of incompetent *Homo sapiens*. At that time, perhaps in countries like France or New Zealand which have had the tradition of liberal beliefs and welfare-state practices, the elite would take care of the masses even when the masses are incompetent. But this would not be the case in countries like the USA where capitalist ideas dominate. Therefore, it can be concluded that the other narratives that are dominant in the future would influence the manner in which we would legitimize the narrative of equality in the society (Harari, 2018).

In my opinion, we live in an era where we do understand that no one narrative would remain the same or dictate our life forever. It is as though the postmodern notion of “incredulity towards metanarratives” (Lyotard, 1984) is applicable in today’s society. Human society is constantly evolving. Narratives rise and fall; and we believe in them and lose faith in them. It is through the collaboration of these narratives that we try to comprehend life, legitimize knowledge and attribute a sense of meaning to our lives.

Significance for the Present-day Context

We can conclude that imagined realities or myths enable human beings to legitimize knowledge and cultural practice as well as coordinate activities in large numbers with one another. Although the human race has survived and become a dominant species on earth for several years owing to these imagined realities, there is a

thin line between these fictions and reality. For instance, although money is an imagined reality that we believe in, humans who possess more currency notes or money are able to equip themselves better and buy more goods and services. This divides the society into classes, where some human beings belong to the privileged classes and some belong to the middle-class community. This, however, is a reality (Harari, 2018).

Thus, when imagined realities materialise into assets, they cause inequality in the society since these assets are not equally distributed. I concede with Harari, that the greatest asset in today's society is data and whoever would own the data would own the future. Moreover, ownership of data would cause inequality in the society and would change the way we comprehend the narrative of equality.

In the present times, we view the liberal narrative with scepticism since we are losing faith in individuality and rationality. We do understand that what gave "*Homo sapiens* an edge over all other animals and turned us into masters of the planet was not our individual rationality, but our unparalleled ability to think in large groups" (Harari, 2018).

Even though we are viewing the liberal narrative with a sceptical lens, we are not losing faith in the narrative of equality. This may be owing to other narratives that exist in the present-day society, for instance the narrative of feminism. Feminism advocates gender equality; there is an attempt to uplift women and prevent women from being exploited. Even the narratives that serve to fight for the rights of the transgender and LGBTQ communities have become dominant today ensuring equality.

Despite this, there are instances of inequality in the societies but there are also endeavours by several people to fight against inequality. For instance, the murder of the African-American

man George Floyd was owing to racial discrimination and police brutality. However, there were several protests among the masses after the murder against systemic racism and police brutality. Slogans such as “Black Lives Matter” were raised and the masses fought to ensure justice and equality.

Several efforts are taken by the government of countries to ensure equality. In the light of the recent coronavirus pandemic, the governments did take measures to take care of the people belonging to lower classes and underprivileged communities. There are certain non-government organizations (NGO’s) that aim to uplift the backward communities and ensure that their rights are protected. So, although there are instances of inequality and discrimination, there are also instances of equality and empowerment in the present-day society. We have not lost faith in the narrative of equality. This is also because of the narrative of human rights which is one of the greatest narratives which the humankind believes in.

Thus, it can be concluded that in terms of the present-day context we have still not completely lost faith in equality. Some inequality may exist in the society that benefits the privileged classes but we have not completely lost faith in the narrative of equality. The government has always taken ways to ensure equality of different communities. In future, like Harari suggests, if we come up with a global endeavour for collective ownership of data, then probably equality would still prevail, for instance like we have the WHO which looks after healthcare on a global level or the United Nations that looks after welfare and promotes harmony among different nations operating on a global level. Thus, if we come up with a body that looks after ownership of data on a global level, we will have equality prevailing to some extent.

Conclusion

From the above article, we can conclude that narratives enable us to legitimize knowledge and help human beings to coordinate activities. One narrative cannot dictate our life forever; moreover, narratives evolve with time. Narratives constantly rise and fall and it is through the collaboration of several narratives that we attribute a sense of meaning to our lives. We can conclude that the narrative of equality has changed and evolved with time and that other narratives have influenced the way in which we comprehend equality over the years. Liberalisation has had an impact on how we comprehend equality and even though we may lose faith in the liberal narrative, we have not completely lost our faith in equality. This may be owing to other narratives like feminism and human rights that exist in the present-day society. Lastly, ownership of data would have a significant impact on how we would legitimize the narrative of equality in future. But our legitimization of equality would also depend on the other narratives that dominate the society in future.

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